

The 2023 Wearable Photoplethysmography Roadmap

Author Guidelines

Thank you for offering to contribute to this Roadmap on wearable photoplethysmography. This document sets out the expectations for contributions.

What is a Roadmap?

[Roadmaps](#) are forward looking articles which contain a set of evidence-based perspectives on the future directions of a field. They are typically single articles composed of short, strictly formatted sections, each written by a leading voice in their sub-field. A Roadmap typically contains 10-20 sections in total. See [here](#) for example Roadmaps.

Aim

The aim of this Roadmap is to provide direction for future research in the field of wearable photoplethysmography. The objectives are:

- To summarise the most pressing areas for future research.
- To highlight key challenges in these areas.
- To outline the advances required to overcome these challenges.

It is hoped that the Roadmap will be a useful resource to researchers when planning their future studies.

Structure and Format

Length: Each section should be around 2 pages (1,400 words) in length.

Format: Sections should be submitted in Word Format (download the template <insert link>).

Title: Should be short (preferably < 50 characters, e.g. 'Atrial fibrillation detection').

Abstract: none required.

Sub-sections: Sections should include the following sub-sections:

- **Status:** *This section provides a brief history and status, why the field is still important, what will be gained with further advances. (400 words max)*
- **Current and future challenges:** *This section discusses the big research issues and challenges. (400 words max)*
- **Advances in science and technology to meet challenges:** *This section discusses the advances in science technology needed to address the challenges. (400 words max)*
- **Concluding Remarks:** *Include brief concluding remarks. This should not be longer than a short paragraph. (150 words max)*
- **Acknowledgements:** *Please include any acknowledgements and funding information as appropriate.*
- **References:** *Limit of 10 References. Please provide references in the Harvard alphabetical style (described [here](#)), including the full author list, and article title, for each reference.*

Figures: Maximum of 2 figures, which should be both included in the text, and provided as separate graphics files (EPS format where possible, or failing that TIFF, JPEG, or PDF as described [here](#)). If the figure is reproduced or adapted from another non-IOP publication, you must seek permission for re-use from the publisher.

Tables: Roadmaps do not usually contain tables. If you would like to include a table then please enquire first.

Audience

This Roadmap is directed towards a multi-disciplinary audience, and it is expected to be of interest to a range of researchers (based in industry and academia), engineers (software, hardware, product design), clinicians, and decision makers. It is also intended to be accessible to people from a range of professional backgrounds (such as in academia and industry), and all levels (from undergraduate students to group leaders). Therefore, the language used should be accessible. However, portions of each section are unlikely to be accessible to a wide audience, and this is acceptable (and to be encouraged when providing specific details which will help direct future research).

Authorship

Each section is normally authored by just 1-3 experts. Do feel free to ask others to co-author your section with you (up to a maximum of 3 authors in total, including yourself).

Internal Review

During the internal review process each author will be asked to review one section other than their own.

Publication

This Roadmap will be submitted to [*Physiological Measurement*](#).